
EMERGING TECHNIQUES IN VISION-BASED HUMAN POSTURE DETECTION: MACHINE LEARNING METHODS AND APPLICATIONS

Benji Peng
Research Scientist
AppCubic
benji@appcubic.com

Keyu Chen
Georgia Institute
of Technology
kchen637@gatech.edu

Ming Li
Georgia Institute
of Technology
mli694@gatech.edu

Pohsun Feng
National Taiwan Normal University
41075018h@ntnu.edu.tw

Ziqian Bi
Indiana University
bizi@iu.edu

Junyu Liu
Kyoto University
liu.junyu.82w@st.kyoto-u.ac.jp

Qian Niu*
Kyoto University
niu.qian.f44@kyoto-u.jp

ABSTRACT

Human posture detection is a rapidly evolving field with significant implications for various applications, including healthcare, surveillance, and human-computer interaction. The continuous advancements in vision-based machine learning approaches have largely improved the accuracy and efficiency of human posture estimation. This review article focuses on some key aspects in this domain such as open datasets for training and validation, 2D and 3D detection methods, and novel image/video-based approaches, thereby offering an overview of the latest innovations.

Keywords Computer Vision · Human Posture Detection · Image Segmentation · Machine Learning · Motion Detection · Motion Analysis

1 Introduction

Human pose estimation (HPE), a well-established and extensively-studied field in computer vision (CV). [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] HPE determines the spatial configuration of human body parts from sensor data, particularly images and videos, providing valuable geometric and motion insights, with applications ranging from human-computer interaction [9, 10, 11] and motion analysis [12, 13, 14] to Extended reality (XR) [15, 16] and healthcare [17, 18, 19]. Recent advancements in deep learning [20, 21, 22] have significantly enhanced HPE [23, 24, 25], outperforming previous methods in various metrics. While novel models structures has led to remarkable progress in HPE, challenges still persist such as object occlusion, deformation, and insufficient high-quality training data.

Despite some inaccuracies and over-generalization, many articles in the past have surveyed and compared different machine learning models in 2D and 3D HPE [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. Tremendous advancements in computing power and model design over the past two years has enabled researchers' increasingly in-depth studies on new tools such as

vision transformers [32], large language models [33], and multi-modality fusion [34]. This article introduces those new breakthroughs, focusing on the improvements researchers have relentlessly made upon existing models and their explorations of novel architectures.

2 Datasets For Human Pose Estimation

Datasets are key inputs for human pose estimation (HPE) research, enabling the development and evaluation of algorithms. This section presents the widely used datasets for assessing 2D and 3D deep learning-based HPE methods. These datasets attempt to provide diverse and challenging scenarios, facilitating the advancement of HPE techniques and allowing for fair comparisons among different approaches.

2.1 Datasets for 2D HPE

COCO dataset: Originally released in 2014 as the Microsoft Common Objects in Context (MS COCO) dataset [35], COCO contains 91 common object types with a total of 2.5 million labeled instances in 328k images. It contains more than 200,000 labeled subjects with 17 joints keypoints for HPE.

MPII Human Pose: The MPII Human Pose dataset is a comprehensive resource for 2D human pose information, consisting of around 40,000 images (28.8k training and 11.7k testing) [36]. Images in the dataset cover 800 different human activities and have rich set of labels including positions of body joints.

PoseTrack: PoseTrack is a large-scale benchmark for video-based human pose estimation and articulated tracking. It is a diverse dataset that contains more than 153k poses in single frames and videos [37].

HiEve: Human-in-Events or HiEve (Human-centric video analysis in complex Events), is a large-scale dataset with comprehensive annotations. It contains a record more than 1 million poses, with a number (56k) of action instances during complex events. It also has an average trajectory length of more than 480 frames [38].

2.2 Datasets for 3D HPE

CMU Panoptic Dataset: Has 480 VGA camera views and more than 30 HD views. It has 65 sequences (5.5 hours) and 1.5 millions of available 3D skeletons [39, 40, 41].

Human3.6M: The Human3.6M dataset [42] is one of the largest motion capture datasets of 3.6 million accurate 3D Human poses by recording 5 female and 6 male subjects under 4 viewpoints. Video data is acquired at 50 Hz using four high-resolution progressive scan cameras. Human3.6M dataset covers 17 different scenarios, offering precise 3D joint positions and high-resolution video recordings.

MPI-INF-3DHP: A large monocular 3D pose dataset captured in both indoor and outdoor environments, with 1.3 million frames [43].

3DPW: 3D poses in the wild dataset is recognized as the first dataset in the wild to provide accurate 3D poses for evaluation. This dataset is notable for including video footage captured from a moving phone camera. It consists of 60 video sequences, each annotated with 2D poses and highly accurate 3D poses derived using a method that integrates video data with IMU sensors, effectively handling complex scenes. Additionally, camera poses for every frame in the sequences are provided, along with 3D body scans and models that are re-poseable and re-shapeable. [44]

AMASS: AMASS, Archive of Motion Capture As Surface Shapes, is a large database of human motion unifying different optical motion capture datasets that are marker-based. AMASS contains 40 hours of motion data over 344 subjects and 11265 motions [45].

3DOH50K: The first 3D human occlusion dataset. It contains 50310 training images and 1290 test images, providing 2D, 3D annotations and SMPL parameters for mesh generation [46].

3 Evaluation Metrics

In this section, commonly used performance evaluation metrics for 2D and 3D deep learning-based HPE models are briefly introduced to better understand and compare model performance across publications.

3.1 Metrics for 2D HPE

Percentage of Correct Keypoints (PCK) measures the accuracy of key-point localization within a given threshold. A higher PCK value indicates a better model performance [47].

Average Precision (AP) and Average Recall (AR): Precision indicates how many of the predicted positives are actually correct. It is defined as the ratio of true positive results to the total number of positive predictions made by a model. Recall measures a model’s ability to identify all relevant instances, indicating the extent of the actual positives that are correctly identified. It is defined as the ratio of true positive results to the total number of actual (ground truth) positive instances in the dataset. Mean average precision (mAP) is calculated by averaging the precision values at different recall thresholds for each class or category, and then calculate averages across all classes. mAP provides a comprehensive measure on a model’s accuracy in detecting objects correctly [48], often shows up in 2D HPE model evaluation.

3.2 Metrics for 3D HPE

MPJPE, or mean per joint position error, is recognized as the most widely used metric for evaluating the performance of 3D HPE models. It is calculated by computing the Euclidean distance between the estimated 3D joint positions and the corresponding ground truth positions. i is the joint index, N is the total joint number, J_i is the ground truth 3D position of joint i , and \hat{J}_i is the estimated joint i location.

$$\text{MPJPE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|\hat{J}_i - J_i\|_2$$

By averaging these distances across all joints, MPJPE provides a quantitative measure of the accuracy of the estimated 3D poses [42]. MPJPE has an variant called Procrustes-aligned MPJPE (**PA-MPJPE**). It is the MPJPE after rigid alignment of the predicted pose and ground truth.

MPJAE, or mean per joint angle error, is used to evaluate the accuracy of 3D human pose estimation models by measuring the error in the predicted joint angles by comparing the estimated joint angles with the ground truth angles for each joint in the human body. The errors for all joints are averaged to provide an overall measure of the angular accuracy of the estimated pose. Procrustes-aligned MPJAE, or **PA-MPJAE**, accounts for differences in scale, rotation, and translation between the estimated and ground truth joint angles.

PVE (Per-Vertex Error), also known as **V2V** (Vertex-to-Vertex Error), is a metric used to evaluate the accuracy of 3D shape or mesh reconstruction models, particularly for human pose and shape estimation. This metric measures the error between the estimated and the ground truth 3D mesh vertices.

4 Methods and Models for Human Pose Estimation

Early work addressed challenges in HPE by decomposing the target image by extracting image features, then applying structured prediction globally to infer the overall pose [34, 49, 50, 47]. Thanks to the fast adoption of convolutional neural networks [51, 52, 53] significant improvements to HPE has been made [54, 55]. HPE has been notably driven by the development of diverse neural network architecture, especially since the recent breakthroughs in the vision transformers [56].

4.1 General Approaches For Pose Estimation

HPE utilizes information from images or video sequences [31, 26, 29], with an overall objective to accurately identify the position and orientation of critical body parts via various methodologies. HPE can be predominantly divided into two categories, 2D and 3D, related but each has its unique set of techniques.

4.1.1 2D Human Pose Estimation

When the input contain only one single person, 2D HPE methods focus on localizing that individual’s joints. There have been two popular categories of deep learning techniques for this: regression methods and heatmap-based methods. Regression methods directly map the input image to the coordinates of body joints, typically with fully-connected (FC) prediction layers, eliminating the need for heatmaps [57]. [58]. Instead of predicting joint coordinates directly, heatmap-based methods estimate 2D heatmaps where each heatmap contains a 2D Gaussian distribution centered at the ground-truth joint position. Those heatmaps are then converted into joint coordinates [59, 60], which can be used for downstream tasks.

Multi-person HPE is inherently more challenging because it requires detecting multiple people in one input, localizing all the joints, and correctly associating those joints with the corresponding individual. To solve this problem, top-down and bottom-up approaches are typically used. Top-down approaches first detect individual persons in the image using a human detector, then apply single-person pose estimation techniques to each detected individual [61]. While top-down methods can be very accurate, they are computationally expensive, especially in images with many people. Bottom-up approaches first detect all possible joints in an image and then group them into individual poses. Although having a higher efficiency comparing to top-down methods, they often face challenges in accurately associating joints, especially in crowded scenes [62].

4.1.2 3D Human Pose Estimation

The development on 3D HPE has made significant strides in recent years, driven by advancements in network structure and the increasing demand for accurate 3D human body representation in various applications [63, 64]. Problems in 3D HPE can be roughly categorized into single-view (monocular) and multi-view 3D HPE, each faces its own unique challenges.

Monocular 3D human pose estimation can be broadly categorized into regression-based and optimization-based methods. Regression-based methods directly estimate 3D human pose from an RGB image using deep networks [65], thanks to the powerful nonlinear mapping capability of neural networks. Various 3D human pose representations are used in regression-based methods such as joint locations [66, 67, 68] and heatmaps [69, 70]. Optimization-based methods, in contrast, incorporate parametric body models like SMPL (Skinned Multi-Person Linear) [71, 65] and fit body models to 2D observations in an iterative manner. For multi-person 3D HPE, top-down [72] and bottom-up [65] approaches similar to 2D HPE have been developed.

Earlier 3D HPE methods directly lift 2D pose estimations to 3D space (2D to 3D lifting), suffering from issues such as inherent ambiguities, complex human-environment intersections, and self-occlusion [73, 74, 75]. Newer approaches [76, 77] introduce intermediate representation into the network and result in better performance.

Multi-view 3D HPE has also been explored to overcome depth ambiguities because different 3d poses may yield identical 2d pose projection. Accessing multi-view cameras could alleviate the ambiguities and achieve desired results [78, 79, 80, 81, 82].

4.2 Novel Human Pose Estimation Models

4.2.1 Vitpose

ViTPose is powered by plain and non-hierarchical vision transformers to extract features from a given image, thanks to ViT’s excellent performance in visual recognition tasks with no specific domain knowledge [83, 84, 85, 86]. Many ViT-based models before ViTPose use CNN as a backbone to extract features [87, 88]. ViTPose, on the other hand, is built directly upon plain ViT (With masked image modeling, MIM, as pretext task [89]) and obtains state-of-the-art performance on the 2D COCO Keypoint dataset [24]. **ViTPose++** was then proposed by the same group of authors to work on multiple types of (heterogeneous) body keypoints [25]. ViTPose++ improved over ViTPose via knowledge factorization [90], which splits fully connected layers into a task-agnostic expert [91] and task-specific experts for better HPE results. Several newer models improved upon ViTPose also have been reported thereafter. **VLPose** utilized visual prompt tuning strategy by freezing the original model weights and incorporating an image prompt and achieved better 2D HPE performance in natural and artificial scenes [92], and **ViPLO** is built upon ViTPose for human-object interaction (HOI) detection [93].

4.3 RTMPose

RTMPose, Real-Time Models for Pose estimation, is a top-down 2D multi-person HPE model with MMPose [94] using an off-the-shelf detector to obtain bounding boxes and then processing each person individually. Top-down HPE approaches typically suffers from latency issues due to the additional detection step, especially in crowded scenes. RTMPose, however, integrates highly efficient real-time detectors to mitigate such shortcoming. The backbone of RTMPose is CSPNeXt [95, 96], a network originally designed for dense prediction tasks comparing to other image classification backbones. RTMPose architecture is further streamlined by employing a minimalistic SimCC-based algorithm for keypoint localization [97]. This algorithm treats keypoint prediction as a classification task, which reduces computational complexity compared to heatmap-based methods. See **Figure 1** The Model’s performance is further enhanced by pre-training the backbone using heatmap-based methods and employing flat cosine annealing [95] during optimization, making it powerful yet highly deployable across various platforms [61].

Figure 1: The overall architecture of RTMPose. A Gated Attention Unit (GAU) is introduced to enhance the keypoint representations by integrating both global and local spatial information. Comparing to transformer layers, it has a more efficient design that lowers memory usage while maintaining high performance. The final pose estimation task is improved through adjusting convolutional kernel sizes and implementing separate Gaussian smoothing parameters for horizontal and vertical coordinates. Figure from Jiang et al. [61].

Figure 2: The Dual-stream Spatio-temporal Transformer (DSTformer) model structure by Zhu et al. Figure from [98].

4.3.1 DSTformer

DSTformer, or MotionBERT, provides a unified framework for learning transferable human motion representations. During pre-training on large-scale, diverse video data sources, a Dual-stream Spatio-temporal Transformer (DSTformer) is used in the motion encoder to reconstruct 3D motion from noisy and incomplete 2D skeleton data (2D-to-3D lifting task). DSTformer uses both mocap data and 2D skeletons extracted from in-the-wild RGB videos, combining 3D reconstruction and 2D re-projection losses. The learned motion representations, embedding geometric, kinematic, and physical knowledge, demonstrate significant transferability to various downstream tasks.

DSTformer is designed to capture long-range spatio-temporal dependencies among skeletal joints through dual streams of multi-head self-attention (MHSA) blocks. The spatial and temporal block models capture both intra-frame relationships and inter-frame dynamics, achieving state-of-the-art results on Human3.6M and 3DPW datasets. The dual-stream approach allows the network to fuse spatial and temporal features adaptively, enhancing the representation’s robustness and versatility see **Figure 2**.

4.3.2 Stacked Hourglass Network

Inspired by Toshev et al.’s work [57], which utilized a deep neural network to directly regress the x, y coordinates of joints, and Tompson et al.’s approach [54], which generated heatmaps by passing images through multiple resolution banks in parallel to simultaneously capture features at different scales, Newell et al. proposed the stacked hourglass (SHG) network to estimating 2D human pose from images [99], resulted in a significant advancement in human pose estimation. The SHG network utilizes repeated symmetric hourglass-like architecture, motivated by the need to capture multi-scale information within an image. The network is structured by using convolutional and max pooling layers to reduce features to a very low resolution. At each max pooling stage, additional convolutions are applied at the pre-pooled resolution. It then performs up-sampling after the lowest resolution, and combines features across scales in a top-down (from low resolutions to high resolutions) manner. Nearest neighbor (NN) up-sampling is used to bring together information from two adjacent resolutions, followed by element-wise addition of the feature sets. Once the network reaches its output resolution, two rounds of 1x1 convolutions are applied to produce the final predictions, a set of heatmaps, where each heatmap predicts the probability of a joint’s presence at each pixel [99].

Graph stacked hourglass (**GraphSH**) networks is built upon graph convolutional network architecture (GCN performs convolution operations on graph-structured data like human skeleton, enabling effective 3D HPE [100, 101]) for

Figure 3: Graph Stacked Hourglass Networks. Input 2D joints are pre-processed by the graph convolution layer and then fed into the hourglass module. Intermediate features are fed into the subsequent hourglass module except the last one figure from Xu & Takano [103].

Figure 4: Overview of the Hourglass Tokenizer (HoT), figure from Li et al. [103].

image-based inputs and achieved state-of-the-art results on the Human3.6M dataset[102]. Unlike other GCN-based methods, which may suffer from limited feature expressiveness, GraphSH introduces a multi-scale, multi-level feature learning approach. It has a repeated encoder-decoder structure processes features at three skeletal scales and captures both local and global spatial information. Intermediate features from various network depths can be integrated, which is instrumental to multi-scale feature processing and final representation enrichment. The model structure of GraphSH is shown in **Figure 3**.

Li et al. recently proposed a plug-and-play pruning-and-recovering framework, called Hourglass Tokenizer (**HoT**) for video-based 3D HPE on Human3.6M and MPI-INF-3DHP datasets. Initially, redundant pose tokens from video frames are pruned using a Token Pruning Cluster (TPC) by dynamically selecting a few representative tokens that retain high semantic diversity, thereby reducing redundancy. Subsequently, a Token Recovering Attention (TRA) module restores the full-length temporal resolution of the pose tokens, ensuring accurate 3D pose estimation while maintaining computational efficiency [103]. HoT seamlessly integrates into existing video pose transformers models, preserving the temporal receptive field necessary for capturing long-range dependencies while minimizing the computational burden. By pruning tokens along the temporal dimension, the framework significantly reduces floating-point operations (FLOPs) without compromising performance, see **Figure 4** for HoT.

4.3.3 SelfPose3d

Designed to bridge the gap between learning-based and optimization-based 3D HPE, **SelfPose3D** is an interesting self-supervised approach estimating 3D poses of multiple persons from multiple camera views [82]. SelfPose3D is built upon VoxelPose by using its output 3d poses as a bottleneck representation [104] and only uses multi-view input images from calibrated cameras and 2D pseudo poses.

In SelfPose3D, target localization is trained on synthetically generated 3D points, representing people’s root positions, and their corresponding 2D root-heatmaps are projected onto each view. During 3D pose estimation, bottleneck representations of localized persons are mapped onto all views to obtain 2D joints, which are rendered as 2D Gaussian heatmaps in an end-to-end differentiable manner. An adaptive attention mechanism is used to handle inaccuracies in pseudo labels, focusing on more reliable regions with hard attention for joint loss supervision and soft attention for heatmap loss supervision [82], see **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Overview of self-supervised SelfPose3d. A self-supervised learning objectives to 3d roots (mid-hip location of the person) localization and 3d poses estimation is proposed. Figure from Srivastav et al. [82].

5 Challenges and Future Directions

Despite substantial advancements in human posture estimation (HPE) through deep learning and advanced network designs, numerous challenges persist in both 2D and 3D contexts. The detection reliability, especially under significant occlusion and in crowded scenarios, will continue as a challenge. Computational efficiency and model scalability still needs further improvement, even some existing methods have achieved near real-time processing on specialized hardware. Real-world applications in gaming, augmented reality (AR), and virtual reality (VR) require more efficient HPE methods on commercial-grade endpoint devices to enhance user experiences. The scarcity of data for rare poses further complicates HPE. Existing open datasets are adequate for common pose estimation tasks but lack sufficient training data for unusual poses, such as falling and injuries. Furthermore, high-quality 3D ground truth pose annotations depend on motion capture systems, which are not easily deployed in arbitrary environments. Consequently, existing datasets are predominantly captured in controlled settings, resulting in state-of-the-art methods under-performing when applied to in-the-wild data.

To address these issues and promote further progress in HPE research, several promising future directions have been identified. The improvement of neural processing units (NPUs) on mobile devices since 2022 enables accelerated on-device learning and inference [105, 106], facilitating real-world applications. Various methods to reduce model size and enhance efficiency [107, 108], as well as the integration of multi-modal large language models (LLMs) in HPE, hold potential. Moreover, novel self-supervised learning frameworks [109, 110] and reinforcement learning could be used to improve HPE, addressing the lack of high-quality datasets on rear poses.

Self-supervised learning: Self-supervised learning uses large amounts of unlabeled data to learn useful representations, addressing the scarcity of high-quality datasets. Self-supervised frameworks has been used in studies like multiple animal tracking [111], group activity recognition [112], and ergonomics risk assessment [113]. A few new models have emerged that could inspire future HPE. For example, **SignBERT+** is self-supervised pre-trainable model use the hand pose as a visual token for sign language comprehension [114]. **EgoFish3D** performs self-supervised learning under multi-view constraints without the need for 3D ground truth annotations [115]. **PanoPose** tries to estimate motion differences between two panoramic images under large viewing angle differences using a self-supervised network [116].

Integrating multi-modal large language models (MLLMs): Multi-modal LLMs, which process and integrate information from various data types such as text, images, and audio, can enhance the robustness and accuracy of HPE by combining contextual and semantic information from multiple input sources [117, 118]. MLLMs have already shown great potentials in autonomous driving [119], remote sensing [120], and video content comprehension [121]. More particularly, **KOSMOS-1** developed by Microsoft research is a multimodal language model that can perceive general modalities as it follows instructions and perform in-context learning for not only language tasks but also multimodal tasks [122]. **mPLUG-Owl** series, mPLUG-Owl [123], mPLUG-Owl2 [117], and mPLUG-Owl3 [124], developed by Alibaba group demonstrate multi-modal abilities through modularized learning of foundation LLMs, which excels in multi-modal instruction understanding and multi-turn dialogues. **ChatPose** understands and reasons about 3D human poses from images or texts [125].

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